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YOUTH GAMBLING IN NIGERIA: HOW PERSONALITY TRAITS SHAPE MOTIVATION IN AUTA BALEFI COMMUNITY

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ABSTRACT: A survey of the influence of personality traits on gambling motivation was conducted among youths in Auta Balefi of Karu LGA, Nasarawa State, Nigeria. Data were collated from a sample of 250 youths in Auta Balefi of Karu LGA. Participants were drawn through the purposive sampling technique. The participants were 55.6% males and 44.4% females with ages from 20 to 50 years. The big-five personality inventory (BF 10 Version) and gambling motivation scale were used to elicit responses from the respondents. Data were analysed using regression and correlation analyses. Openness to experience, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness and neuroticism has their independent degrees or strengths of relationship with gambling motivation among youths of Auta Balefi. It was also revealed that openness to experience, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness and neuroticism jointly and positively predicted gambling motivation among youths of Auta Balefi. More so, personality traits contributed to 26.3 % variability in explaining gambling motivation. On the individual dimensions, openness to experience, conscientiousness, extraversion and agreeableness all significantly predicted gambling motivation among youths in the area. Conversely, neuroticism did not predict gambling motivation among youths in the area. The results indicated that openness to experience; conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness and neuroticism jointly influence gambling motivation among youths in the study area. Based on the findings, the study recommended that parents, government, counselling psychologists, organizations, and even youths should be aware of the disastrous consequences, and programs should be put in place to get youths to adopt healthy attitudes toward gambling.

Keywords: Personality, Personality traits, Gambling, Motivation, Youths

INTRODUCTION

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With the increase in unemployment, idleness and poverty, gambling has become the latest activity among youths in our communities. Hardly is there a community today in Nigeria without a gambling centre, otherwise known as betting centres or shops. Gambling can be defined as pledging money or something of value at risk to win more money or something of greater value. Risking money on the result of something where the outcome is uncertain, like a game, horse racing, and elections is also gambling. Reckless behaviour like rash driving, drinking and driving, substance use, etc., is considered gambling. In other words, gambling is taking a chance. The value pledged on the uncertainty is known as the stake, and people stake money, possessions, and even their lives in various forms of gambling. Gambling is considered a legitimate and natural leisure activity (McMillen, 1996; Gambling is one of the major entertainment and attraction of the tourism industry; since it is available at all times and in most major cities of the world. The development of the casino industries has contributed remarkably to the tourism and growth of most towns (Wan, 2012). Gambling can be used as an attraction to increase tourists to destinations that have lost their charm to attract tourists. Many destinations that otherwise are not visited by tourists are revived due to gambling (Richard, 2010). The gambling industry is a major source of revenue for the government and a valuable source of business for private enterprises. Legalized sports betting is a growing business in many U.S. States and the tax revenue it generates fund various state resources from roads and highways to public education, law enforcement and gambling addiction programs (Grundy, 2024). The gambling industry also helps the locality's economic development. The gaming industry remains a powerful economic engine and a dynamic job creator in USA. Gaming supports more direct jobs than in other industries such as plastics manufacturing, or the motion picture and sound recording industry. Additional highlights. Within the broader gaming industry, commercial casinos employ 361,000 employees who earn \$17.4 billion in wages and benefits while tribal casinos employ 198,000 employees who earn \$9.1 billion of wages and benefits annually (American Gaming Association, 2018). The gambling industry's growth also brings about development in allied services like hospitality services, hotels, restaurants, transportation, real estate, etc. (Ishihara, 2017 Sports betting has slowly emerged as a lucrative segment, leveraging Nigeria's huge football culture. Some of the big leagues, such as the English Premier league, and the Spanish La Liga, have millions of fans in the country - betting provides Nigerians the opportunity to earn from what they love. Despite the temporary dip in economic activities in 2016, growth prospects are positive even as the economy rebounds, and income stabilizes (PricewaterhouseCoopers, 2017) globally, the prevalence rate of gambling differs from country to country. In SubSaharan Africa for instance, a survey carried out in Kenya, Uganda, South Africa, Ghana, Nigeria, and Tanzania of 3,879 youth aged between 17 and 35 found that 54% of youths in these countries have engaged in some forms of gambling activity. Kenya was reported as having 76% of youth who had previously participated in gambling or betting, Uganda 57%, Ghana 42% and Nigeria 77% (Ssewanyana & Bitawire, 2018). The report showed a 9.5% increase in the gambling rate among youths in Nigeria when compared with Eboh & Babatunde, 2015) who reported a 67.5% gambling rate among university students in Nigeria. However, Eboh & Babatunde (2015) attributed the increase in gambling behaviour among youths to the ease of more contemporary patterns of gambling (Temitope, Oyekola & Mary, 2019). Since gambling is considered a human behaviour like any other type of addictive behaviour, it is important to analyse the factors which lead to this particular behaviour. Since individuals engage only in those behaviours, they consider important, it is crucial to analyse personality traits to determine the various antecedents leading to the behaviour. Personality traits are conceptualized as dimensions of individual differences in tendencies to show consistent patterns of thoughts, feelings, and actions across events, developmental periods and contexts (McCrea & Costa, 2003). Personality traits are characteristics and qualities that help define you as a unique individual. They're often developed throughout life and may remain consistent across many situations and circumstances (Dudfield et al., 2022). These traits are enduring characteristics that are consistent and stable across time and situations. Personality is immensely complex. The most prominent and psychometrically supported model of personality in psychology is McCrae and Costa's (2003) five-factor model of personality (Baranczuk,

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2019). According to the five-factor model of personality, five broad domains of personality can describe between-person differences in human personality. These five domains of personality are openness, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness and neuroticism (McCrae & Costa, 2003). Openness is the tendency to be imaginative, curious, and have an open mind; conscientiousness is the tendency to be well organized, goal-oriented, and self-disciplined; extraversion is the tendency to be assertive, energetic, and sociable; agreeableness is the tendency to be affectionate, cooperative, helpful, and trusting; neuroticism is the tendency to feel anxious, irritable, depressed, and insecure (Mackinnon, Lambe & Stewart, 2016; Shum, O’Gorman, Creed & Myors, 2017). Individual personality differences are likely to play an important role in explaining the propensity to gamble. One of the potential roadblocks to elucidating the relationship between personality and gambling may be inadequately accounting for the diversity of gambling activities. Personality traits represent characteristic ways of thinking, feeling, and behaving, and are robust predictors of health-risk behaviours, important life outcomes and gambling (Temitope et al., 2019). Extensive literature implicates the role that personality traits play in shaping behaviour, including behavioural disorders such as disordered gambling (Slutske, 2005). It is therefore surprising that a consensus has not yet been reached about the personality traits that are related to the propensity to gamble. Understanding the role that personality plays in influencing gambling behaviours has the potential to elucidate the individual-level aetiology of disordered gambling and may have implications for treatment; for example, an individual whose gambling is motivated by negative effect may require a different treatment approach than one who is driven by impulsivity. The diversity of gambling activities poses a challenge when trying to understand the relationship between personality and gambling. Another variable of interest is gambling motivation. Motivation is the force that activates, intensifies and leads to behaviour and persistence. Motivation, when considered from the subjective perspective, is quite a simple concept. It is as simple as people trying to get something since they want to have it. The want factor is the motivation that leads to behaviour. Motivation and social orientation play an important role in determining an individual’s future; hence their behaviour is controlled by these forces (Varlinskaya, 2010). Motivation is the underlying reason for people to engage in certain behaviour. It is important to study the motivation leading to action to understand any form of behaviour (Tom, 2020). Gambling motivations are important factors influencing gambling behaviour. According to Boyle & Vallieres (2001), gambling is a motivational consequence that leads people to become involved in betting and invest a considerable amount of time and money. Gambling behaviour is decided by the various motivational factors which lead people to be involved in the behaviour. Examining gambling motivations will help analyze why people choose to gamble (Lee, Lee, Bernhard & Yoon, 2006). Psychological and social motivations can be used to control gambling behaviour, which indicates the importance of motivation in gambling behaviour (Breen, Hing & Gordon, 2011; Potenza, Wareham, Steinberg, Rugle, Cavallo, Krishnan-Sarin & Desai, 2011). Dudfield, Malouff, and Meynadier (2022) examined the associations between five-factor personality model traits using a meta-analysis. The authors hypothesized that high neuroticism, low conscientiousness and low agreeableness would be associated with problem gambling because these personality traits have been found to be associated with other types of addictive behaviour involving alcohol, cannabis, tobacco, and internet gaming. The strongest personality correlates of problem gambling were neuroticism, followed by conscientiousness, agreeableness, openness, and extraversion. The results suggest problem gamblers tend to share a common personality profile – one that could provide clues as to the most effective ways to prevent and to treat problem gambling (Dudfield et al., 2022). Temitope et al. (2019) carried out a study on personality traits and financial strain as determinants of gambling behaviour among youth in Nigeria, using youths in Oyo State and Ekiti State as a case study. The research design adopted in the study was the descriptive research design of correlational type. The study adopted the multi-stage random sampling technique, with a sample of 320. However, only 297 participants’ responses were retrieved for analysis in the study. Three instruments were used in the study. They are; Gambling behaviour scale developed by Jeffery (2010), which was used in measuring the prevalence and pattern of gambling behaviour, The Big-five

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personality scale developed by Goldberg (1993), which was used in assessing the personality domain of an individual and the Financial strain scale developed by Aldana & Liljenquist (1998), used in measuring the rate of financial strain experienced by people. The results of the study revealed that personality characteristics and financial strain predict gambling behaviour among youths in the study area. The result also reveals that there is a significant difference in gambling behaviour of male and female youth in the study area, indicating that male youths exhibited more gambling behaviour compared to their female counterparts. On the premise of these findings, the authors recommended that youths are to be trained on how to improve their behavioural attitudes and should be well-guided to avoid gambling because it has serious effects on their psychological health and overall well-being (Temitope et al., 2019). Gambling as a form of leisure is gaining popularity in most of the world (The Economist, 2014; Markham & Young, 2015). Many countries promote gambling for government revenue (Rintoul, Livingstone, Mellor, & Jolley, 2012; Young, Doran & Markham, 2013). Along with the mushrooming of casinos and sports betting centres, gambling problems are also on the rise. With the addition of new gambling products, casinos and sports betting centres/platforms are now managing to target, market, and engage different community sectors, attracting more and more people into gambling. This has led to an exponential daily increase in the rate at which Nigerian youths are engaging in various forms of gambling. Hardly would one find any clusters of youth that are not ruminating or getting involved in gambling activities. More so, the time that is supposed to be invested into profitable activities and endeavours are wasted on argument and speculations on gambling results and related activities by most youths. Gambling poses health and social risk to individuals and their families (Wheeler, Round & Wilson, 2010; Williams, Rehm & Stevens, 2011), as this behaviour often results in behavioural, emotional, relationship, or financial problems which may develop into a diagnosable condition known as pathological gambling if not properly handled. Also, the high availability and easy accessibility of various patterns of gambling render many youths vulnerable to gambling. Consequently, as a result of onset and continued gambling, many youths experience bankruptcy, loss of job, broken homes, substance use abuse, depression, maladjustment, and frustration among others. Indeed, the potential danger of gambling behaviour on the health and social lives of youths cannot be overemphasized if not properly managed. To mitigate the costs associated with gambling behaviours and to use it to advantage is important to find the various personality traits that lead to gambling and the factors that moderate gambling behaviour. It is against this backdrop that this study aims to assess the influence of personality traits on gambling behaviour among youths in Auta Balefi area of Keffi LGA, Nasarawa State.

The study aimed at assessing the influence of personality traits on gambling motivation among youths in Auta Balefi of Karu LGA, Nasarawa State. Its specific objectives were to:

- i. Determine the independent relationship between openness to experience, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness and neuroticism subscale on gambling behaviour among youths of Auta Balefi.
- ii. Examine the joint influence between openness to experience, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness and neuroticism subscale on gambling behaviour among youths of Auta Balefi.

Research Hypotheses

The following posited research hypotheses guided the study:

- i. There will be an independent relationship between openness to experience, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness and neuroticism subscale on gambling motivation among youths of Auta Balefi
- ii. There will be a joint influence between openness to experience, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness and neuroticism subscale on gambling motivation among youths of Auta Balefi.

METHOD

Research Design

The study adopted the survey design.

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Participants

A total of 255 participants will be selected among youths in Auta Balefi, Karu LGA of Nasarawa State, with no preference given to their gender. The accidental sampling method will be used to select participants for the study using the following inclusion criteria: a) Participants must be between the ages of 19 and 45 years of age

- b) Participants must have engaged in gambling for not less than six months
- c) Participants must be a resident of Auta Balefi.
- d) Participants must be providing informed consent.

Method of Data Collection

Two separate instruments were administered in this study. They are:

The Big-five Personality Inventory

The Big five inventory (BFI) is a 44-item inventory developed to assess the five dimensions of personality. The BFI is a 44-item inventory that assesses personality from a five-point dimensional perspective. This perspective shows that personality characteristics can be resolved into five broad dimensions which are peculiar from one another. These five areas of BFI are extraversion, neuroticism, agreeableness, openness to experience and conscientiousness. The original psychometric properties for the Americans sample were provided by John, Donahue and Kentle (1991), while Umeh (2004) provided the psychometric properties for the Nigerian sample. The coefficient of reliability provided by John et al. (1991) is Cronbach Alpha of .80, test-retest reliability of 0.85. The mean convergent validity coefficient of BFI is 0.75 and .85 in addition to the Big Five Instruments co-authored by Costa and McCrae (1992) and Golberg (1992) respectively. Tafida, Nweze and Udegbe (2018) also reported a reliability coefficient of 0.84 for the Big five inventory (BFI). The items on the BFI will be scored as follows: Strongly disagree = 1, Disagree = 2, Undecided = 3, Agree = 4, strongly Agree strongly = 5. This study used the Big Five Inventory 10 (BFI 10) version, adapted from Rammstedt and John (2007).

Gambling Motivation Scale (Chantal et al., 1995)

The Gambling motivation scale (GSM) is a 28-item rating scale developed by Chantal et al. (1995) and a measure of gambling involvement. The GSM is derived from the tenet of self-determination theory (Deci & Ryan, 1991; Ryan & Deci 2000), and contains 28 items representing potential answers to the question: why do you gamble? These items are scored on a 7-point Likert-type scale anchored by the endpoints does not correspond at all (1) and correspond exactly (7), with the midpoint of corresponds moderately (4). The GSM comprises of seven subscales which are Intrinsic Motivation to Know, Intrinsic Motivation to Accomplish, and Intrinsic Motivation to Express Stimulation, Identified Regulations, Introjected Regulation, External Regulation and Amotivation. The internal consistency values (Cronbach's alphas) of the seven subscales as established by Chantel et al. (1995) were Intrinsic Motivation to know (0.81), Intrinsic Motivation to accomplish (0.78), and Intrinsic Motivation to Express Stimulation (0.73), Identified Regulations (0.64), Introjected Regulation (0.80), External Regulation (0.77) and Amotivation (0.78). Prior to administering the research instrument to the participants of the study, the researchers introduced her to the respondents and presented valid student identification, explain the aim and objectives of the study, and solicited their voluntary participation in the study. After the introduction, the researcher administered the instrument to interested respondents, with instructions and a guide on how to address the items on the instrument. To maintain anonymity and confidentiality, respondents were instructed not to write their names, identification marks, or numbers anywhere on the instrument. More so, the researcher took the liberty of assuring the respondents of the study that confidentiality will be strictly adhered to. Hence, all the information they provided will only be used for this research purpose and no personal information will be disclosed. The respondents were given an hour to respond to the research. For respondents who cannot understand the research instrument, the researcher guided them on how to attend to the instrument.

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics analysed the socio-demographic characteristics of the participants, while inferential statistics such the Pearson Product Moment correlation analysed the independent relationship between openness to experience, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness and neuroticism subscale on gambling motivation

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among youths of Auta Balefi, while the multiple regression analysis determine the joint influence between openness to experience, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness and neuroticism subscale on gambling motivation among youths of Auta Balefi.

RESULTS

Socio-demographic Characteristics of the Participants of the Study

From the Table 1, it can be observed that the demographic characteristics of respondents of the study with respect to their age distribution reveal that 60.8% of the respondents were between the age group of 20 and 30 years, while those within the age bracket of 31 and 40 years accounted for 25.2%. In like manner, it was revealed that the participants within the age bracket of 41 – 50 years of age accounted for 14%. The sex (gender) variable recorded among the respondents of the study revealed that the majority of the participants were males, with a 55.6% share, while female respondents accounted for 44.4%.

Table 1: Socio-demographic characteristics of participants of the study

Variables	Frequency	Percentage of distribution
Age	20 – 30 years	130
	31 – 40 years	54
	41 – 50 years	30
	Total	214
Sex	Male	119
	Female	95
	Total	214
Marital status	Single	121
	Married	58
	Divorced	35
	Total	214
Religious affiliation	Christianity	117
	Islam	97
	Total	214
Educational Background	No formal education	20
	Primary	19
	Secondary	51
	Tertiary	124
	Total	214
Occupation	Trader/business	61
	Government/Private	87
	Others	66
	Total	214

Source: Field survey, 2023.

The findings on the socio-demographic characteristics of the participants revealed three statuses associated with the state of the marriage of respondents, who are single accounting for 56.5%. Respondents who were married accounted for 27.1%, while 16.4% were divorced. The results also revealed that 54.7% of the participants were Christians, while 45.3% were Muslims. The assessment of the educational background of the respondents in the study area revealed that respondents with a tertiary level of education constituted 57.9%, while those with secondary school education constituted 23.8%. The data further reveal that 8.9% of the participants possessed primary school education, while those with informal education accounted for 9.4%. The results also revealed the various occupations of the participants, with a majority being either government employees or employees in the private sector, as indicated by a 40.7% response rate, while 28.5% were traders/business persons(s). The result further revealed that 30.8% of participants engaged in various forms of occupations.

Hypotheses 1:

There will be an independent relationship between openness to experience, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness and neuroticism subscale on gambling motivation among youths of Auta Balefi. From the results, the Pearson correlation coefficient indicates a weak relationship between openness to experience and gambling motivation (intrinsic motivation to know) ($r = -.124, p = .071 > 0.05$). More so, this relationship was not statistically significant. Conscientiousness had a non-statistically weak relationship with intrinsic motivation to know gambling motivation ($r = -.032, p = .637 > 0.05$). Extraversion had a moderate positive relationship ($r = .403, p = .403 > 0.05$) with intrinsic motivation to know gambling motivation. Agreeableness recorded a very

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strong negative relationship with intrinsic motivation to know gambling motivation ($r = -.089$). This relationship was however not statistically significant ($p = .195 > 0.05$). In like manner, neuroticism showed a very strong negative relationship with intrinsic motivation to know gambling motivation ($r = -.089$). This relationship was however not statistically significant ($p = .161 > 0.05$).

Tale 2: Correlations results on the independent relationship between gambling motivation among youths of Auta Balefi

		Extraversion	Agreeableness	Conscientiousness	Neuroticism	Openness to Experience
Intrinsic motivation to know	Pearson Correlation	.058	-.089	-.032	-.096	-.124
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.403	.195	.637	.161	.071
	N	214	214	214	214	214
Intrinsic motivation toward accomplishment	Pearson Correlation	.141*	-.016	.186**	-.010	-.162*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.040	.821	.006	.888	.018
	N	214	214	214	214	214
Intrinsic motivation to experience stimulation	Pearson Correlation	.217**	.287**	.286**	.217**	.289**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.000	.000	.001	.000
	N	214	214	214	214	214
Extrinsic motivation - identified	Pearson Correlation	.047	.264**	.058	.051	.083
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.497	.000	.399	.459	.226
	N	214	214	214	214	214
Extrinsic motivation - introjected	Pearson Correlation	.148*	.288**	-.180**	.122	.066
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.030	.000	.008	.074	.333
	N	214	214	214	214	214
Extrinsic motivation - external regulation	Pearson Correlation	.136*	.200**	.136*	.120	.063
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.048	.003	.047	.079	.363
	N	214	214	214	214	214
Amotivation	Pearson Correlation	.019	.115	.083	.250**	.235**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.787	.094	.228	.000	.001
	N	214	214	214	214	214

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).
 * . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The gambling motivation subscale of intrinsic motivation toward accomplishment had a weak positive relationship with extraversion. More so, this weak positive relationship with this personality trait was statistically significant ($p = .040 < 0.05$). Intrinsic motivation toward accomplishment recorded a non-statistically negative relationship with agreeableness ($r = -.016, p = .821 > 0.05$). However, intrinsic motivation toward accomplishment positively (weak) and significantly correlates with conscientiousness ($r = .186, p = .006 < 0.05$). Neuroticism negatively correlates with intrinsic motivation toward accomplishment. This weak negative relationship was not significant ($r = -.010, p = .888 > 0.05$). Similarly, openness to experience negatively correlates with intrinsic motivation toward accomplishment. This weak negative relationship was however statistically significant ($r = -.162, p = .018 < 0.05$). The result revealed a positive and significant weak relationship between the gambling motivation subscale of intrinsic motivation to experience stimulation and extraversion ($r = .217, p = .001 < 0.05$). In like manner, intrinsic motivation to experience stimulation showed a positive and significant weak relationship with agreeableness ($r = .287, p = .000 < 0.05$). Similarly, intrinsic motivation to experience stimulation showed a positive and significant weak relationship with conscientiousness ($r = .286, p = .000 < 0.05$). More so, intrinsic motivation to experience stimulation showed a positive and significant weak relationship with neuroticism ($r = .217, p = .001 < 0.05$). Furthermore, intrinsic motivation to experience stimulation showed a positive and significant weak relationship with openness to experience ($r = .289, p = .000 < 0.05$). The gambling motivation subscale of extrinsic motivation – identified revealed a positive moderate relationship with extraversion ($r = .047, p = .497 > 0.05$). This moderate relationship between these two variables was not statistically significant. Extrinsic motivation – identified showed a positive and significant weak relationship with agreeableness ($r = .264, p = .000 < 0.05$). The results also revealed positive moderate relationship between extrinsic motivation – identified and conscientiousness ($r = .058, p = .399 > 0.05$). This moderate relationship was however not significant. In like manner, extrinsic motivation – identified showed a non-statistically positive moderate relationship with

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Neuroticism ($r = .051, p = .459 > 0.05$). In like manner, a non-statistically strong positive relationship was established between extrinsic motivation – identified and openness to experience ($r = .083, p = .226 > 0.05$). The gambling motivation subscale of extrinsic motivation – introjected showed a weak positive and significant relationship with extraversion ($r = .148, p = .030 < 0.05$). In like manner, the results weak positive and significant relationship between extrinsic motivation – introjected and agreeableness ($r = .288, p = .000 < 0.05$). The results revealed a weak negative and positive and significant relationship between extrinsic motivation – introjected and conscientiousness ($r = -.180, p = .008 < 0.05$). Neuroticism showed a non-statistically weak positive relationship with extrinsic motivation – introjected ($r = .122, p = .074 > 0.05$). Openness to experience showed a non-statistically moderate positive relationship with extrinsic motivation – introjected ($r = .066, p = .333 > 0.05$). The extrinsic motivation - external regulation subscale showed a weak positive and significant relationship with extraversion ($r = .136, p = .048 < 0.05$). In like manner, the results revealed a weak positive and significant relationship between agreeableness and the extrinsic motivation - external regulation subscale ($r = .200, p = .003 < 0.05$). Conscientiousness also had a weak positive and significant relationship with extrinsic motivation - external regulation ($r = .136, p = .047 < 0.05$). Neuroticism recorded a nonstatistically weak positive relationship with extrinsic motivation - external regulation ($r = .120, p = .079 > 0.05$). Similarly, openness to experience recorded a non-statistically weak positive relationship with extrinsic motivation - external regulation subscale of gambling motivation ($r = .063, p = .363 > 0.05$). The relationship between the gambling motivation subscale of amotivation and the various personality traits under consideration in the study revealed a non-statistically significant weak positive relationship between amotivation and extraversion ($r = .019, p = .787 > 0.05$). The results also revealed a non-statistically significant weak positive relationship between amotivation and agreeableness ($r = .115, p = .094 > 0.05$). Conscientiousness had a non-statistically strong positive relationship with amotivation ($r = .083, p = .228 > 0.05$). However, neuroticism had a positive weak and significant relationship with amotivation ($r = .250, p = .000 < 0.05$). In like manner, openness to experience had a positive weak and significant relationship with the gambling motivation subscale of amotivation ($r = .235, p = .001 < 0.05$).

Hypotheses 2:

There will be a joint influence between openness to experience, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness and neuroticism subscale on gambling motivation among youths of Auta Balefi.

Table 3: Multiple linear regression scores showing the joint influence of openness to experience, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness and neuroticism subscale on

gambling motivation among youths s in the study area							
Predictor variable	R	R ²	df	F	β	t	Sig
Constant	.513	.263	5	41.206		11.116	.001
			209				
Openness to experience					.429	8.357	.005
Conscientiousness					.212	.4.242	.001
Extraversion					.216	3.645	.001
Agreeableness					.239	.4.877	.002
Neuroticism					.075	1.449	.148

Criterion Variable: Gambling motivation

Source: Author’s computation, 2023.

The Table 3 indicated that openness to experience, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness and neuroticism jointly and positively predicted gambling motivation among youths of Auta Balefi [$F = 41.206; P < .01$]. This result implies that the various personality traits (openness to experience, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness and neuroticism) jointly influence gambling motivation among the participants of the study in the area also significantly. The result further revealed that the personality traits accounted for 26.3 % (R^2

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= .263) variability in explaining gambling motivation among youths in the study area. On the individual dimension, personality traits such as openness to experience ($\beta = .429$; $P < 0.05$); conscientiousness ($\beta = -.212$; $P < 0.05$), extraversion ($\beta = .216$; $P < 0.05$) and agreeableness ($\beta = .239$; $P < 0.05$) all positively predicted gambling motivation among youths in the study area, except for neuroticism ($\beta = .075$; $P > 0.05$).

Summary

This study examined the influence of personality traits on gambling motivation among youths in Auta Balefi of Karu LGA, Nasarawa State, Nigeria. The survey research design was used due to the researcher's inability to directly manipulate the variables of the study. Data used in the study were collated from youths in Auta Balefi of Karu LGA. The sample consisted of 250 out of which 214 were used. The participants of the study were made up of 119(55.6%) males and 95(44.4%) females with ages ranging from 20-50 years. Participants were drawn through the accidental sampling technique. The big-five personality inventory (Brief 10 Version) and gambling motivation scale were used to elicit responses from the respondents used for the study. Data collated were analysed using regression and correlation analysis. Results of the study revealed that openness to experience; conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness and neuroticism have their various independent degrees/strengths of relationship with gambling motivation among youths of Auta Balefi. It was also revealed that openness to experience, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness and neuroticism jointly and positively predicted gambling motivation among youths of Auta Balefi [$F = 41.206$; $P < .01$]. This finding is in agreement with the work of Dudfield et al. (2022) and Temitope et al. (2019) as pointed out in the empirical review. More so, personality traits contributed to 26.3 % ($R^2 = .263$) variability in explaining gambling motivation among youths in the study area. On the individual dimensions, openness to experience ($\beta = .429$; $P < 0.05$); conscientiousness ($\beta = -.212$; $P < 0.05$), extraversion ($\beta = .216$; $P < 0.05$) and agreeableness ($\beta = .239$; $P < 0.05$) all significantly predicted gambling motivation among youths in the study area. These findings conform to the report of Temitope et al. (2019), Ucheagwu et al. (2019; 2022) and Oyeleke et al. (2017). Conversely, neuroticism ($\beta = .075$; $P > 0.05$) did not predict gambling motivation among youths in the area. Finally, the results indicated that openness to experience, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness and neuroticism jointly influence gambling motivation among youths in the study area and significantly [$F = 41.206$; $P < .01$], conforming with the results of the study carried out by Bagby et al. (2007).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

On the premise of the results of the study, it was concluded that openness to experience, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness and neuroticism have various independent relationships with gambling motivation among youths of Auta Balefi. On independent dimensions, openness to experience, conscientiousness, extraversion and agreeableness all significantly predicted gambling motivation among youths in the study area, except for neuroticism. Jointly, openness to experience, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness and neuroticism influences gambling motivation among youths of Auta Balefi also significantly.

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

- 1) Parents, government, counselling psychologists, organizations, and even youths should be aware of the disastrous consequences, and programs should be put in place to get youths to adopt healthy attitudes toward gambling, such that they recognize it is not a way to make money, nor is it a healthy way to escape from life stressors and for parents to be more involved in the life of their wards to tackle the menace of gambling behaviour.
- 2) Therefore, there is a need to create awareness of the rate at which gambling activities are increasing and their negative consequences.
- 3) Furthermore, youths should be encouraged to adopt better ways of making money and a healthy way to escape from life stressors rather than gambling. A recreation centre and youthful program that can create a sense of livelihood and excitement should be created.

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